

THE ERA OF STRANGE LEARNING STRATEGIES -Garbhasanskar , Google SMS
Channels & U-Learning as strange Learning Strategies

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Abstract:

In this research paper we will discuss about some strange learning strategies as **Garbhasanskar , Google SMS Channels & U-Learning** in a series. It is well clear that learning is a life-long continuous process which goes from Womb to Tomb . So a good teacher or good parents must take care for the learning of his/ her wards since the time of their conception. It is not new concept but almost no one employs it at the pre-natal stage of development. Since the conception of the child in the womb of his/ her mother, learning starts automatically but who cares for it yet everybody know about the positive effects of Garbha Sanskar. So, it is very strange phenomenon that almost everyone has forgotten the importance of GARBHASANSKAR due to his/ her busy life and the increasing modernity but this old technique of learning must be revived and made applicable in the present day society.

Google SMS Channels is also one of the new inventions in informal learning without spending even penny. The school managements must made provision for E-classes & U-learning to facilitate learning. With the progress in Educational Technology, the concept of e-learning and m-learning now got transformed into u-learning.

On the basis of Socratic Method of teaching ,the subject matter of the different subjects can be split into short question and very short answer form booklet . Students may be directed to set up some National or World record without taking any risk to his/ her own life. It will make them enthusiastic that is the pre-requisite for good learning.

In nutshell, our research paper will focus on age old Garbhasanskar technique, M-learning by Google SMS channel learning, E-learning by E-classes, U-learning, teaching by framing very short question & answer , importance of setting up some National or World

record, replacement of Government Management from Govt schools by N.G.O.s , introduction of the variety of prizes in disciplines of regularity, punctuality,creativity not only to students but to teachers too to have properly motivated students and teachers.

Keywords: Pre-Natal Stage, Garbhasanskar, Garbhasanskar Camps, S.M.S. Channels, P.D.A's(Personal Digital Assistance), Ubicomp, Ubiquitous Learning Environment, RFID (Radio Frequency Identification)

Introduction:-

We are living in an era of new discoveries & rapid growth. Science is making progress day by day. So, our teaching-learning strategies must be progressive with the scientific age to be effective. Science has made our living strange .So, let us see how science can re-shape our educational practices. Science has now began the era of strange learning strategies. Under this head of the strange learning strategies, we will discuss mainly about three learning strategies as *Garbhasanskar* , *Google SMS Channels* & *U-Learning* as Strange Learning Strategies. Now, let us see *What is Strange in these strange learning strategies ?*

Garbha-Sanskar as Strange Learning Strategy:-

If we know the importance of a thing but don't use that thing but after some time realising the importance of that thing and making its use can be termed as new thing. Like this, i am talking about the Garbha-Sanskar as learning strategy which is not new but it should be treated as new since everyone knows about it but almost no one takes it seriously. **Watson**, the famous environmentalist, once declared, "*Give me any child, I will make him/her what you desire.*"

But Now the question arises that which environment plays the major role-- pre-natal or post-natal environment in the proper development of the foetus/embryo in the womb.? Watson, the famous environmentalist, is emphasizing on the post-natal environment as in above definition but in my opinion , pre-natal environment is the most impressive period of development. Now,let us see that what is Garbha-sanskar ? Garbha-sanskar word is made up of two words Garbha and Sanskar which means "*In Womb*" and "*An Impression On Memory*" respectively which implies a strategy by which we can form everlasting impression on the memory of the children in the womb of his /her mother. Every family must co-operate the expectant during her pregnancy period since the first three months are very important

period in the brain development of the child. If we can provide rich and peaceful environment to the expectant than surely we can have Abhimanyu, Prahalad and Ashtavakra and even more than them. Stories of Abhimanyu and Ashtavakra from the Indian Epic Mahabharata and the story of Bhakt Prahalad from the Puranas clearly shows the importance of the pre-natal period.

Central and State Governments must take this strategy seriously by providing so many books and cd's on Garbha-Avastha and Yoga to the village level libraries. The expectant may read jokes, religious scriptures, bhajans, motivational quotations and they can also listen to the vedic music to develop the proper emotions, attitudes, instincts in the child. Besides this **Garbhasanskar Camps** can be organized to provide all the necessary care and experiences to the pregnant under one roof by the experts from time to time . NGO's can play a great role in the organisations of Garbhasanskar Camps in the rural & urban areas. These N.G.O.s can direct the group of pregnant ladies socially about the *DO'S & DONTS'* of pregnancy period.

"*Garbh Se Shuru Hoti Garbh Ki Pathshala*" an article by Vijaya Kathale Nibanthe published in November,2007 edition of GrihLakshmi magazine stated that garbhasanskar technique is more useful in Maharashtra state of India. James Nicholas is organising Garbhsanskar camps in Maharshttra for last few years. Garbhsanskar Guru Dr Gitanjali Shah also advocates the importance of this technique .A latest news which was published in esteemed newspaper- Hindustan on dated 23rd feb, 2012 on page no.16 by title "*Garbh Me Hi Tay Ho Jati Hai Pasand* " also highlighted the importance of the pre- natal period.

Google Sms Channels as Learning Strategy:-

Under the series of the *Strange Learning Strategies*, now we will focus on the use and importance of Google Sms Channels. As everybody is aware about the growing benefits of Educational Technology in the field of Education especially Distance Education. The concept of e-learning and m-learning is now considered as an old concept and the latest concept of learning must be the mixture of the both of the above mentioned old concepts i.e. learning via information technology via mobile as i think of it. Let us see what is the e-learning & m-learning.

- *E-Learning* is a subset of *Distance Learning* -- *Mobile Learning* is a Subset of *E-Learning*.

- “ E-Learning is the use of network technology to design, deliver, select, administer, and extend learning.” – *Elliott Masie, The Masie Center*
- *E-learning* includes all forms of electronically supported [learning](#) and [teaching](#), and more recently [Edtech](#).
- Abbreviations like CBT (*Computer-Based Training*), IBT (*Internet-Based Training*) or WBT (*Web-Based Training*) have been used as synonyms to e-learning.
- [Mobile Learning](#) is the ability to obtain or provide educational content on personal pocket devices such as PDAs, smartphones and mobile phones.

Every regular/ private institute must be well acquainted with various sites which allows their users to send free sms to any person individually or to the whole group to let their students to avail their benefits. One of such popular website is [way2sms.com](#) .But there is also some unique plan of google to send and receive free sms to unknown persons via creating or subscribing free sms channels without knowing or disclosing anyone's identity.

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/settings?cr=in&continue=/smschannels/browse>

One can learn while doing his/her routine work i.e. while doing any work, if u have your mobile with you then you can make proper use of your time by reading the received sms in your mobile's inbox to remain up-to-date in your field of study.

Really, it is very very amazing, exciting and interesting. I have created various free sms channels groups but it is not enough to create these channels as after channel creation it becomes very important for the channel owner to make it popular by copying the channel subscription link from the channel's homepage and pasting it in e-mails and also on various link posting websites such as [indiastudychannel.com](#). Now let us discuss about the whole process step by step by which we can register ourselves with google sms channels to send and receive free messages by/on our mobiles

Steps to use Free Google sms Channels:-

- 1- Create your email account on google or gmail .
- 2- Before subscribing to or creating an sms channel , you/ one need to login through your new gmail account username and the same password on the [labs.google.co.in](#) link and then

select your nickname and verify your mobile number by entering it in the space provided there.

3- Existing gmail a/c holders must login by their gmail user name and password only on the labs.google.co.in/smschannels/browse go to the right side box on the main home page of labs.google.co.in search for the existing channels for the required category. on the left side of this page, you will also see a option for sorting the existing sms channels such as :- sort by most users, recent channels, recent posts, narrow by category and narrow by location.....

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/browse?cat=All&ctab=Browse&select=city%3ANone%2Cstatus%3AAll&cr=in>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/browse?cat=All&sort=1&ctab=Browse&select=city%3ANone%2Cstatus%3AAll&cr=in>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/browse?cat=All&sort=2&ctab=Browse&select=city%3ANone%2Cstatus%3AAll&cr=in>

4-Subscribe the channels of your interest by switching/ pressing the "**SUBSCRIBE**" button there. you may subscribe to maximum 22 number of sms channels through one gmail id/ mobile number.

5-The front bar on the home page of labs.google.co.in shows the following buttons:-

Web Reader SMS Channels more skb0071979@gmail.com | My Account | Settings | Help | Sign out Browse Channels My Channels

6-You can create your own sms channel too to circulate your sms to your known or unknown persons.you may post maximum 3 sms per day (sms character length:- 140)per channel.

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/help?cr=in>

http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/help?cr=in#create_channel

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/help?cr=in#subscribe>

http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/create_channel?cr=in&continue=&prev=

7-You can invite the persons whose email id or mobile number you know to join your sms channels.

8-You can also change your google free sms account settings by pressing the settings button on the front bar of the home page. in this section, you can change your nickname,registered phone number,maximum messages per day, range of time for getting daily free sms.<https://www.google.com/settings/>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/settings?cr=in&continue=/smschannels/browse%3Fcat%3DAAll%26ctab%3DBrowse%26select%3Dcity%253ANone%252Cstatus%253AAll%26cr%3Din>

9-In addition to this you may create your free account on way2sms.com to send 140 characters long english language 500 sms daily to the mobile number of any individual or to groups formed up by you.you may also receive email/gmail notifications on your mobile by adding a forwarding address in forwarding section/ forwarding and POP/IMAP of the settings of your gmail account.

The free google sms channels created by me are as follows :-

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/kbcQuestions>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/dailyhindiquotes>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/EnglishLiterature2012>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/RelationshipOf7withGK>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/annaagainstcorruption>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/forugnetineducation>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/EnglishLiteratureskb>

<http://labs.google.co.in/smschannels/subscribe/investmentIdeas>

Besides this,Science@Mobile Scheme by IGNOU is to circulate free sms of science like interesting science facts, latest science news, health tips, green tips, events and days of scientific importance on mobile by registering at <http://scienceatmobile.ignou.ac.in/>

'Science@Mobile' is an innovative scheme by IGNOU's National Centre for Innovations in Distance Education (NCIDE) in collaboration with Vigyan Prasar.

U-Learning as Learning Strategy:-

With the progress in Educational Technology, the concept of e-learning and m-learning now got transformed into u-learning. Physical devices in e-learning is wired & in mobile learning, is wireless & in u-learning, it disappears. In e-learning, learning is confined to single desk while in u-learning, it is very much flexible. U-learning is 24x7 type learning. So, now i will explain Ubiquitous Computing or u-computing which is the combination of e-learning and m-learning. The term Ubiquitous Computing was first coined by the late Mark Weiser, a researcher at Xerox Palo Alto Research Center (PARC) in the late 1980's which refers to the process of seamlessly integrating computers into the physical world. Mark Weiser in 1991 stated that *'the most profound technologies are those that disappear.....'*

Wikipedia states that Ubiquitous Learning is equivalent to a form of simple mobile learning e.g. learning environments that can be accessed in various contexts & situations but infact u-learning is not simple mobile learning, it is more than that or we can say that it is the mixture of the both types of m & e learning. Ubiquitous Computing (often abbreviated as "*UbiComp*") is the idea that almost any device from tea cup, clothes to cars and even human body can be embedded with chips to connect the device to an infinite network of other devices. Embedded means the extent to which the physical environment is encoded with intelligent technology (introduction of artificial intelligence) such as sensors and smart tags or bar code & bar code readers.

There are various *Elements of Ubiquitous Computing* such as Nanotechnology (use of Micro-Processors), Wireless Computing (use of Bluetooth & Wi-Fi Technology), Context-Awareness (use of Sensors & RFID tags) & Natural Interaction which offers a powerful set of tools to achieve the aim of u-learning. Microprocessors with memory having information about the objects will be embedded in every object/device & it will release the stored information about the object at the arrival of the student near the object. ULE Server Module will include the server, the educational strategies unit & a database. Sensors will be placed adjacent to the objects/ devices to detect any changes in the surroundings.

Tim *Kindberg and Armando Fox* observed that *Physical Integration and Spontaneous Inter-Operation* are the two key characteristics of the u-learning. A UbiComp System involves some integration between computing nodes and the real world. In ubiquitous system,

components must spontaneously inter-operate in the changing environments. Important characteristics of the U-Learning are :

- Permanency,
- Accessibility,
- Seamlessness,
- Immersion,
- Context-awareness,
- Adaptability,
- Calmness,
- Interactivity,
- Immediacy,
- Self-Regulated Learning

Students learn automatically within the u-space or U.L.E. or *Ubiquitous Learning Environment*. Now let us define U.L.E.. It is a setting in which students become totally busy in the learning process automatically. Ubiquitous means omnipresent, pervasive or everywhere. Learning means instructive or pedagogical while Environment means surroundings, setting or situation. So, U.L.E. is a setting of omnipresent instruction. In U.L.E., education happens all around of the student consciously or unconsciously. Only the presence of the students is quite enough to let them learn in U.L.E. Each student becomes part of the many to one relationship within the u-space. According to Vicki Jones & Jun H. Jo, there are two main factors in U.L.E. model i.e. 'what' and 'the how'. The 'what' factor indicates to the ULE model itself which uses a wireless network with both Wi-Fi and Bluetooth and the 'how' factor indicates the inclusion of pedagogical information which is based on the constructivist theory which allows the students to create knowledge from what they see, hear, read & perceive by interpreting their surroundings.

In the U.L.E., each student carries a wireless device (Personal Digital Assistance PDA's or mobile phone) fitted with headphones. Sensors help the ULE server module to track and locate each student within the u-space. When the student approaches an object, then data from that object transmits to the student's handheld device. Ubiquitous technology plays a major role in all aspects of R&G (Robotics & Games) research. In the u-learning mode/system, based on the educational activities & on the location & time of

interactions, there are three types of learning modes- Synchronous, Asynchronous & hybrid mode.

Examples of U-Learning:-

- An exclusive article entitled "*Chinta Chhodo , Chip Se Jiyo*" which was published in Amar Ujala newspaper on dated 29th march, 2012 on Hi-Tech page highlighted the SMART-UNIFORM experiment of a Brazilian school which is also based on u-computing. In this school, students wear the Smart Uniforms in which Sensors are fitted in such a manner that when students reaches the entry gate of their schools, electronic readers read their presence along with arrival time and informs their positions to their parents by sms .

- **R. Jason Weiss & J Philip Craiger** explained the importance of *Ubiquitrain System* which is based on a database of training content to which users connect via desktop computers & wireless handheld devices.

- **An Intelligent Fractions Learning System-A Conceptual Design by Teemu H.Laine, Andrew Cyrus Smith and Thato Foko.** In this system, U-fractions is ULE which combines mobile technology, tangible fraction blocks & a story based game into a mathematical learning experience.

- Another example of u-learning is **Computer Supported Ubiquitous Learning Environment For Vocabulary Learning Using RFID Tags By Hiroaki Ogata, Ryo Akamatsu, and Yoneo Yano.** It provides Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) in U.L.E. They called it TANGO (Tag Added Learning Objects) system. In this model, the system detects the objects around the learner using the RFID(Radio Frequency Identification) tags and provides the learner the right information regarding language learning.

There are much finest examples of u-learning systems. Now, U-learning environments can be set up with the help of the Educationists & the software/hardware Engineers. On the basis of Socratic Method of teaching, the subject matter of the different subjects can be split into short question and very short answer form booklet .Traditional learning environments can be translated into digital format by providing the students PDA's like palmtop, pocket pc, tablet pc, laptop etc and expanding wireless infrastructure by providing technical experts to schools. Battery charging problem of Handheld Devices restricts the wide expansion of U-learning. Solid solution to battery charging is yet to be found by inventing wireless energy transfer which is now at testing stage. Govt. must create innovative Digital Learning

Environments & redesign classroom architecture by replacing Government Management from Govt schools by N.G.O.s to increase the efficiency of institutions. Students may be directed to set up some National or World record without taking any risk to his/ her own life. It will make them enthusiastic that is the pre-requisite for good learning. The variety of prizes in disciplines of regularity, punctuality, creativity may be introduced not only to students but to teachers too to have properly motivated students and teachers.

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